

Photochemistry of 3-alkoxy chromones : Photocyclisation of 3-benzyloxy-6-chloro-2-(1'-methyl-2'-phenylvinyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran

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Abstract : Photocyclisation of 3-benzyloxy-6-chloro-2-(1'-methyl-2'-phenylvinyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran with pyrex filtered UV light to yield linear tricyclic pyranopyrone and angular fused tetracyclic compound is described. The product formation occurred via cyclisation of 1,4-biradical produced through H-abstraction by C=O group and conrotatory 6π -electrocyclisation.

Keywords : Styrylchromones, pyranobenzopyrones, photocyclisation.

Introduction

Intramolecular H-abstraction reactions in 3-alkoxy-2-arylchromones¹ are of considerable interest in synthesis of fused linear² and angular³ tetracyclic compounds. Photocyclodehydrogenation of stilbenes⁴ and their analogous 2-styrylchromones⁵ is reported to be a potential synthetic method for polycyclic aromatic compounds. In our earlier communication we reported that 3-alkoxy-2-styrylchromones² on photoirradiation were transformed into linearly fused 2,3-pyranopyrones through the intermediacy of 1,4-biradicals. In the present study, we des-

cribe our investigation on photolytic behaviour of 3-benzyloxy-6-chloro-2-(1'-methyl-2'-phenylvinyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran in order to get better understanding of

Results and discussion

how role of insertion of electron releasing methyl group on triene system affects the product formation. The methanolic solution of 3-benzyloxy-6-chloro-2-(1'-methyl-2'-phenylvinyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran **5** on photoirradiation with pyrex filtered UV light furnished four products **6** (10%), **7** (72%), **8** (6.0%) and **9** (4.0%) (Scheme 1). The yields of photoproducts have been calculated by excluding the yield of the starting compound recovered.

Scheme 1. Photoirradiation of 3-benzyloxy-6-chloro-2-(1'-methyl-2'-phenylvinyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran.

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The structures of the compounds **5-9** were confirmed from their spectral data. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **6** showed the absence of proton signal at δ 6.65 (as ob-

served in ^1H NMR spectrum of **5** due to ethenic proton) and upfield shifting of $-\text{CH}_3$ absorption (δ 2.09 in **5** to δ 1.23 in **6**), thereby indicating the involvement of styryl moiety in photocyclisation. The stereochemical disposition of H-2, H-3 and H-4 in **6** was derived from their coupling constants ($J_{2,3}$ and $J_{3,4}$ 10.2 Hz), which showed *trans* orientation of H-2 and H-3 as well as H-3 and H-4. The C-4 methyl, C-2 and C-3 phenyl groups occupy more preferred equatorial positions² with ring C assuming inverted half chair conformation (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

The elemental and spectral analysis of **7** showed it to be isomeric with **5**. It showed identical 300 MHz ^1H NMR chemical shift and coupling pattern and also identical mass spectrum with **5**. Photolysis of compound **7** under same conditions provided a mixture of **5**, **6**, **7**, **8** and **9** with same equilibrium composition as in photolysis of **5**.

The IR spectrum of **8** showed carbonyl absorption at 1646 cm^{-1} (cf. **5** 1655 cm^{-1}) showing it to be a highly delocalized system. The M^+ peak in mass spectrum of **8** at m/z 294 (100%) showed loss of mass unit 108 (benzyl alcohol) from **5** during photolysis. The structure of compound **8** was further proved by 300 MHz ^1H NMR in which H-1 appeared as doublet (J 9.0 Hz) at δ 9.95 owing to deshielding⁶ effect of C=O group at C-12. The identity of photoproduct **8** was further confirmed by preparing an authentic sample of the compound through photochemical cyclisation of 6-chloro-2-(1'-methyl-2'-phenylvinyl)-chromene-4-one⁷.

The novel compound **9** showed carbonyl stretch at 1661 cm^{-1} in its IR spectrum and ^1H NMR exhibited no signal in aliphatic region except CH_3 (δ 2.42, s). The mass spectrum showed highest ion at m/z 310 (100%) and the presence of rDA fragment at m/z 155 (15%) confirmed the presence of intact benzopyran moiety in **9**. The elemental analysis and ^{13}C assignments proved the structure of **9** which is being named as 7-chloro-3-methyl-2-phenyl-1,4-dioxacyclopenta[*b*]naphthalene-9-one.

Regarding mechanistic considerations, the formation of products **6-9** can be well envisaged to occur through competitive photo-excitation of C=O and triene system (Scheme 2). The photo-conversion of **5** to **6** may be explained through an initial H-abstraction from the alkoxy group by the photo excited C=O of pyrone moiety followed by cyclisation and 1-5 H shift, as also observed in our earlier studies⁸. The pathway to yield **7** is *cis-trans* isomerisation of 1'-2' double bond, common in such alkene systems⁹. The formation of compound **8** must involve the conrotatory photocyclisation of 6π triene system through **7**, favored by low $\pi-\pi^*$ energy gap due to electron releasing inductive effect of methyl group. The compound **9** is a novel product formed during photolysis of **5** and its generation can be thought to occur through the intermediacy of 3-hydroxychromone which undergoes excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) from 3-hydroxy group to the styryl double bond followed by ring closure and aromatization via expulsion of hydrogen molecule. This mechanism has been proved by formation of **9** through direct photolysis of 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(1'-methyl-2'-phenylvinyl)-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran. This mechanism finds support from the cyclisation of *o*-allylphenols¹⁰ and *o*-hydroxystyrenes¹¹ through ESIPT.

The quenching of C=O excitation in **5** by I_2 during photolysis rendered photoproducts **7** and **8** only, confirming the involvement of both chromophores (carbonyl and triene) in phototransformation. Further it was also found that the photolysis of **7** provided the mixture of **5**, **6**, **7**, **8** and **9**; the ratio of **5** and **7** depends upon irradiation time (vide ^1H NMR). It is worth to mention here that the styryl chromones^{2,8} having no CH_3 attached to styryl C=C did not yield products corresponding to **7**, **8** and **9**.

It may be concluded that due to inclusion of electron releasing methyl group on triene system of 3-benzyloxy-2-styrylchromones, the facile formation of 1,4-biradical by photo-excitation of C=O is competed by the 6π -electrocyclisation and isomerisation of $\pi-\pi^*$ excited triene system. Though the 3-alkoxy-2-styrylchromones^{2,8} are known to yield pyranopyrones, oxetanopyranones and pyranolcohols but to the best of our knowledge this is the first case where their photochemical reaction could lead to the formation of substituted 1,4-dioxacyclopenta[*b*]naphthalene-9-one. Further work to investigate the effect of different alkoxy groups at 3-position of 6-chloro-2-(1'-methyl-2'-phenylvinyl)-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran on product distribution and mechanistic pathway is being carried out.

Scheme 2. Mechanism of product formation through photoirradiation.

Experimental

Synthesis of 3-hydroxy-6-chloro-2-(1'-methyl-2'-phenylvinyl) chromen-4-one :

It was synthesized by condensation of 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone and α -methylcinnamaldehyde ($\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2/\text{ethanol}/\text{reflux}$)¹² followed by H_2O_2 (50%)/ NaOH cyclisation¹³. Yield 40%; m.p. 138–140 °C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}): 1612 (C=O), 3308 br (OH); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.20 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.62 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.50 (1H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-8), 7.70 (1H, d, J_{allyl} 0.9 Hz, H-2'), 6.90 (1H, s, OH), 7.46–7.30 (5H, m, H-2''–6''), 2.38 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 0.9 Hz, 1'- CH_3).

Synthesis of 3-benzyloxy-6-chloro-2-(1'-methyl-2'-phenylvinyl) chromen-4-one :

Compound 5 was synthesized⁸ by O-alkylation of 3-hydroxy-6-chloro-2-(1'-methyl-2'-phenylvinyl) chromen-4-one with benzylchloride (K_2CO_3 , CH_3COCH_3 , $t\text{-Bu}_4\text{N}^+\text{I}^-$). Yield 80%, colorless crystals; m.p. 72–74 °C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}): 1632 (C=O), 1609 (C=C); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.17 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, 5-H), 7.53 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.38 (1H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-8), 7.36–7.21 (11H, m, H-2', 2''–6'', 2'''–6'''), 5.12 (2H, s, 3- OCH_2), 2.05 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, C_1 - CH_3);

^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 173.96, 160.39, 153.33, 142.15, 139.25, 136.89, 136.60, 136.15, 133.55, 130.56, 129.43, 129.13, 128.35, 128.34, 128.26, 127.93, 127.82, 125.07, 119.71, 74.24, 16.07; m/z 402 (M^+ , 100%).

General procedure for the photoirradiation of compound 5 :

A deoxygenated solution of 5 (1.0 g) in dry MeOH (200 ml) was irradiated in a pyrex glass reactor under N_2 atm. with 125 W Hg lamp for 2 h. The red yellow gummy mass obtained after reduced pressure evaporation of solvent was chromatographed over column of silica gel yielding compounds 6, 7, 8 and 9 by eluting with benzene-pet ether.

Compound 6 : Yellow solid (10%), m.p. 175–177 °C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}): 1647 (C=O), 1604 (C=C); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.21 (1H, d, J_m 2.7 Hz, H-9), 7.52 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.7, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.36 (1H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-6), 7.15–6.89 (10H, m, H-2'-6', 2''-6''), 4.90 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 10.2 Hz, H-2), 3.37 (1H, td, J_{vic} 6.6 Hz, $J_{4,3}$ 10.2 Hz, H-4), 2.92 (1H, t, $J_{3,2}$ 10.5 Hz, $J_{3,4}$ 10.5 Hz, H-3), 1.23 (3H, d, J_{vic} 6.6 Hz, C_4 - CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 170.23, 153.06, 152.85, 138.30, 138.07, 137.28, 132.87, 129.85, 128.27, 128.04, 127.64, 127.53,

127.05, 126.87, 125.02, 124.10, 119.05, 82.40, 53.91, 37.20, 15.01; m/z 402 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 74.61; H, 4.70. Calcd. for $C_{25}H_{19}ClO_3$: C, 74.53; H, 4.75%).

Compound 7 : Light yellow (72%), m.p. 52–54 °C; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1643 (C=O), 1608 (C=C); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 8.14 (1H, d, J_m 2.7 Hz, H-5), 7.45 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.22 (1H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-8), 7.36–6.88 (10H, m, H-2''–6'', 2'''–6'''), 6.65 (1H, d, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, H-2'), 4.89 (2H, s, 3-OCH₂), 2.09 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, C₁-CH₃); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 173.59, 159.11, 153.74, 139.57, 137.28, 136.99, 136.22, 134.59, 133.53, 130.69, 128.57, 128.31, 128.07, 127.94, 127.62, 127.33, 125.47, 125.00, 119.73, 73.58, 23.00; m/z 402 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 74.48; H, 4.81. Calcd. for $C_{25}H_{19}ClO_3$: C, 74.53; H, 4.75%).

Compound 8 : Creamy solid (6.0%), m.p. 140–142 °C; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1645 (C=O), 1605 (C=C); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 9.95 (1H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-1), 8.36 (1H, d, J_m 2.7 Hz, H-11), 7.62 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.7, 9.0 Hz, H-9), 7.51 (1H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-8), 7.94 (1H, s, H-5), 7.75 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.1, 8.1 Hz, H-4), 7.67 (1H, dt, $J_{m,o}$ 2.1, 8.1 Hz, H-2), 7.53 (1H, dt, $J_{m,o}$ 2.1, 8.1 Hz, H-3), 2.62 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, C₆-CH₃); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 177.44, 156.77, 152.79, 145.05, 136.51, 133.92, 130.14, 129.93, 128.74, 127.58, 126.68, 126.54, 126.29, 125.96, 125.96, 124.21, 119.30, 16.77; m/z 294 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 73.43; H, 3.69. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{11}ClO_3$: C, 73.35; H, 3.76%).

Compound 9 : Colorless crystalline solid (4.0%), m.p. 165–167 °C; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1659 (C=O), 1608 (C=C); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 8.34 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-8), 7.57 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.4, 9.0 Hz, H-6), 7.49 (1H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-5), 7.82 (2H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 1.8, 8.4 Hz, H-2', 6'), 7.45–7.39 (3H, m, H-3', 4', 5'), 2.42 (3H, s, C₃-CH₃); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 173.10, 163.80, 155.42, 155.33, 154.07, 134.86, 132.94, 130.49, 129.80, 129.56, 128.90, 126.95, 126.06, 119.56, 107.74, 7.96; m/z 310 (M^+ , 100%) (Found : C, 69.62; H 3.49. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{11}ClO_3$: C, 69.58; H, 3.57%).

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